

SUPPLY CHAIN ANALYSIS OF MANGALMURTI BANANA RIPENING CHAMBER, PATHROT DIST: AMRAVATI

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Abstract

The present study, titled "Supply Chain Analysis of Mangalmurti Banana Ripening Chamber, Pathrot, District Amravati", was undertaken to analyze the supply chain framework, estimate the establishment cost, evaluate marketing costs and margins, and identify operational constraints associated with banana ripening chambers. Banana is a vital fruit crop in India, appreciated for its nutritional benefits and perennial availability. Maharashtra, particularly the Vidarbha region, plays a significant role in the country's banana production, thereby necessitating effective post-harvest handling and ripening infrastructure. This case study focuses on the Mangalmurti Banana Ripening Chamber, established in 2008, which employs scientifically controlled ethylene gas methods for uniform ripening and shelf-life enhancement. Two major supply chain channels were identified: Channel I (Producer → Ripening Chamber → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer) and Channel II (Producer → Ripening Chamber → Retailer → Consumer). Among these, Channel II was observed to be shorter and more economically efficient. The establishment cost of the selected ripening chamber was approximately ₹30.74 lakh, with fixed capital forming a substantial portion of the total cost. Marketing expenses were chiefly borne by wholesalers and retailers, and profit margins varied across the intermediaries involved. Key constraints identified include high initial capital requirements, shortage of skilled labour, inconsistent electricity supply, and challenges in procuring quality raw bananas.

Keywords: Banana, Ripening Chamber, Supply Chain, Establishment Cost, Marketing Margin, Constraints, Maharashtra.

Introduction

Banana (*Musa paradisiaca* Linn) is one of the most widely consumed fruits globally and holds significant social, economic, and cultural importance, particularly in India. As the largest producer of bananas, contributing approximately 23% to global output, India harvested 35.36 million metric tonnes in 2022–23, though only 1% was exported, indicating untapped export potential. The fruit's year-round availability, rich nutritional profile—comprising fibre, potassium, vitamin B6, vitamin C, antioxidants, and phytonutrients—makes it a preferred choice across all consumer segments.

Maharashtra is one of the leading banana-producing states, with major production areas including Jalgaon, Nandurbar, Dhule, and Amravati. According to the National Horticulture Board (NHB), the state has a banana cultivation area of 111,003 hectares and a productivity rate of

58.8 tonnes per hectare. Despite its high yield, a significant portion of the produce is sold in domestic markets due to limited export processing infrastructure.

The banana supply chain in India comprises multiple channels, with bananas typically sold in unripe form to wholesalers, retailers, or exporters. Ripening chambers using ethylene gas play a critical role in enhancing fruit quality and shelf life. However, factors such as high establishment costs, inadequate cold chain infrastructure, and inconsistent supply chains affect efficiency and profitability. This study focuses on evaluating the supply chain and operational dynamics of a selected banana ripening chamber in Maharashtra, aiming to identify areas for improvement in cost efficiency, market linkage, and sustainability.

Company Profile:

1. Company Name	Mangalmurti Ripening Chamber
2. Establishment in	2008
3. Owner Name	Sachin Rase
4. Contact Number	9822277472
5. Location	Pathort, Dis: Amravati
6. Rooms	4 Rooms
7. Room Capacity	200 crates, 200 crates, 400 crates,
8. Chamber Capacity	1000 – 1500 Crates

Objectives of study:

To identify supply chain of Banana.

To work out the supply chainwise cost and margin of intermediaries.

Methodology**Area of Study:**

The present study was conducted at Mangalmurti Banana Ripening Chamber, Pathort in Amravati district.

Period of Study:

The Study of supply chain of Banana in Amravati District was done for the year 2024-25.

Source of Data:

The primary data was collected by pretested schedule from farmers, ripening chamber owner, wholesaler and retailer etc. of selected firm by personal interview method regarding the establishment cost, marketing cost and margin etc.

Analytical Tools:**Supply chain of banana:**

The Simple chain analysis was carried out for the present study.

Supply chain wise marketing cost and margin of intermediaries:

Marketing cost: Marketing cost refers to the actual expenses incurred during the marketing process, encompassing the amount spent by producers, sellers, and intermediaries from the time of harvest until the product reaches the final consumer. These costs include activities such as loading, unloading, transportation, weighing, commission charges, labour, packaging, and market fees.

Market margin: The market margin, defined as the difference between the price paid by one intermediary and the price received by the previous one, which reflects the cost and profit associated with the value-adding activities performed by market intermediaries

Market margin is expressed as follows:

$$MM = Sp - (Pp + Mc)$$

Where,

MM – Market margin

Sp – Selling price

Pp – Purchase price

Mc- Marketing cost

Result and Discussion**Supply chain of Banana.**

The two marketing channels were found during the study on Mangalmurti Banana Ripening Chamber in Amravati District which is as follow:

Channel 1: Producer – Ripening Chamber – Wholesaler – Retailer – Consumer

Channel 2: Producer – Ripening Chamber – Retailer – Consumer

Channel 1 of the banana supply chain follows the path: Producer → Ripening Chamber → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer. Raw bananas are first sent to the ripening chamber, where controlled conditions enhance their quality and shelf life. The ripened bananas are then distributed by wholesalers to retailers, who sell them to

consumers. This channel ensures timely delivery of market-ready fruit and adds value, especially during the ripening stage, with each stakeholder playing a key role in maintaining product quality and availability.

Channel 2 of the banana supply chain follows the sequence: Producer → Ripening Chamber → Retailer → Consumer. In this model, bananas are sent directly from producers to ripening chambers, where they are ripened under controlled conditions. The ripened bananas are then delivered straight to retailers, bypassing wholesalers. This reduces handling, lowers costs, and improves profit margins for producers and retailers. The shorter supply chain also ensures better freshness and quality for consumers, making it efficient and suitable for areas with organized retail and good logistics.

Supply chain wise marketing cost and margin of the intermediaries.**Table 1. Marketing cost incurred by intermediaries in Channel I & Channel II**

Sr. no.	Particulars	Channel I Amount (Rs/Qt.)	Channel II Amount (Rs/Qt.)
A	FARMER		
1	Selling price	1300	1400
B	Marketing cost incurred by the ripening chamber		
1	harvesting cost	40	40
2	sorting & grading	20	20
3	weighing charges	10	10
4	loading & unloading	50	50
5	transport	30	30
6	ripening charges	80	80
7	spoilage	20	20
8	miscellaneous	20	20
9	maintenance	10	10
10	Total marketing cost	280	280
C	Marketing cost incurred by the wholesaler		
1	loading & unloading	30	
2	transport	50	
3	storage	15	
4	sorting & package	20	
5	weighing charges	10	
6	commission charges@ 6%	132	
7	labour charges	20	
8	miscellaneous	10	
9	Total marketing cost	287	
D	Marketing cost incurred by the retailer		
1	loading & unloading	15	10
2	transport	10	10
3	commission charges@ 4%	110	100
4	weighing & packaging	10	10
5	miscellaneous	10	10
6	Total marketing cost	155	140
7	Final selling price to consumer	2750	2500

Table 1 shows the comparative analysis of two marketing channels for bananas reveals critical insights into the cost dynamics from farm gate to consumer. In Channel I (Producer → Ripening Chamber → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer), the selling price received by the farmer is ₹1300 per quintal. In contrast, Channel II (Producer → Ripening Chamber → Retailer → Consumer) shows a slightly higher farmer price of ₹1400 per quintal, indicating a direct channel can offer marginally better returns to producers. The marketing cost incurred by the ripening chamber remains constant across both channels at ₹280 per quintal. This cost includes components such as harvesting (₹40), sorting and grading (₹20), weighing (₹10), loading and unloading (₹50), transportation (₹30), ripening charges (₹80), spoilage (₹20),

miscellaneous (₹20), and maintenance (₹10). In Channel I, additional costs are borne by the wholesaler, amounting to ₹287. These include key expenses such as commission charges (₹132, 6% of selling price), transport (₹50), loading/unloading (₹30), sorting/packaging (₹20), and other miscellaneous costs. The retailer in Channel I further incurs ₹155 per quintal, covering commission (₹110), transport, packaging, and minor operational expenses.

For Channel II, which omits the wholesaler, the retailer's marketing cost is slightly lower at ₹140 per quintal, primarily due to reduced commission (₹100) and lesser handling costs. The final price paid by the consumer is ₹2750 in Channel I and ₹2500 in Channel II, indicating

that Channel II is more cost-efficient for the end consumer and allows for a higher producer share in consumer rupees.

Table 2. Market margin incurred by intermediaries in Channel I & Channel II.

Sr. no.	Particulars	Channel I Amount (Rs/Qt.)	Channel II Amount (Rs/Qt.)
A	Ripening chamber		
1	Purchase price	1300	1400
2	Marketing cost	280	280
3	Selling price	1700	1900
4	Margin	120	220
B	Wholesaler		
1	Purchase price	1700	-
2	Marketing cost	287	-
3	Selling price	2200	-
4	Margin	213	-
C	Retailer		
1	Purchase price	2200	1900
2	Marketing cost	155	140
3	Selling price	2750	2500
4	Margin	395	460

Table 2 shows the analysis of margins and cost components in two banana marketing channels highlights the price dynamics and profit distribution among stakeholders. In Channel I (Ripening Chamber → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer), the ripening chamber purchases bananas at ₹1300 per quintal, incurs a marketing cost of ₹280, and sells at ₹1700, yielding a margin of ₹120. The wholesaler then incurs ₹287 in marketing costs and sells at ₹2200, earning a margin of ₹213. The retailer, purchasing at ₹2200 and spending ₹155 on marketing, sells at ₹2750, gaining the highest margin of ₹395.

In contrast, Channel II (Ripening Chamber → Retailer → Consumer) shows higher efficiency. The ripening chamber purchases at ₹1400, spends ₹280, and sells at ₹1900, earning a margin of ₹220, significantly more than in Channel I. The retailer, purchasing at ₹1900 and incurring ₹140 in costs, sells at ₹2500, earning a margin of ₹460, which is also higher than in Channel I.

This comparison indicates that Channel II is more profitable for both the ripening chamber and the retailer, with a lower consumer price (₹2500 vs. ₹2750). The absence of the wholesaler reduces the number of intermediaries, thereby increasing operational efficiency and producer-retailer margins.

Conclusion

The analysis of the Mangalmurti Banana Ripening Chamber in Amravati district presents a comprehensive view of the operational, economic, and logistical aspects of banana ripening and its supply chain. The study identifies two primary supply chain channels for banana distribution, with Channel II (Producer → Ripening Chamber → Retailer → Consumer) proving to be more efficient and economically viable than Channel I (Producer → Ripening Chamber → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer). Channel II is characterized by a reduced number of intermediaries, which leads to lower costs, higher profit margins for producers and retailers, and more competitive prices for consumers. Moreover, the findings highlight the importance of optimizing supply chain strategies, with Channel II representing a model that could be implemented more widely to improve the economic outcomes of banana ripening businesses. Further research is necessary to explore the long-term impact of these strategies on the broader agricultural supply chain.

References

1. **Gaikwad, M. S., Kulkarni, R. N., & Bhapkar, V. S. (2019).** Study on operational economics of banana ripening chambers. *Journal of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development*, 5(2), 122-127.
2. **Ghimire S. B Koirala, S Devkota and G Basnet, (2019):** Economic analysis of commercial banana cultivation and supply chain analysis in Chitwan, Nepal, *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. (5): 190-195.
3. **Naveen, B. et al. 2015.** "Marketing channels and price spread of banana in Chikkaballapur district of Karnataka." *International Research Journal of Agricultural Economics and Statistics*, 6(1): 18-22.
4. **Nayak, Archit Kumar, Nahar Singh and Dinesh Kumar, 2018.** "Economic analysis of marketing of banana (*Musa paradisiaca* L.) in Durg district of Chhattisgarh." *Internat. Res. J. Agric. Eco. & Stat*, 9(1): 1-8.
5. **Sarode, S. C. 2009.** "Economics of banana marketing in Jalgaon district: An analysis across alternative channels." *African Journal of Marketing Management*, 1(5): 128-132.
6. **Srivastava, S. C. and Mishra R. R. 2001.** Price spread and marketing channel of mango in Varanasi district of Uttar Pradesh. *The Bihar Journal of Agricultural Marketing*, 9(3): 273-290.
7. **Takle S.R, P.M. Kalyankar and V.B. Bhise, (2011):** Agricultural Marketing and Supply chain Management of Banana, *International Journal of Business Management, Economics and information Technology*. 3 (2) 335-339.
8. **Vaghasiya, Vishal et al. 2022.** "Banana Supply Chain: A Case Study of Vadodara City of Gujarat." *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 40(12): 424-429.
9. **Vijayan, S.R. and Kumar S. 2023.** "Socio Economic Analysis and Marketing of Poovan and Nendran Banana in Thiruvananthapuram District of Kerala." *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*, 13(8): pp.1857-1865.
10. **Wanjari, V. and Ladaniya M.S. 2010.** "Marketing of banana in selected districts of India." *Tropical Agricultural Research and Extension*, 7.S.